

Talabalarga Interdisiplinar Yondashuv Asosida “Ona Tili – O‘Qish Savodxonligi Va Uni O‘Qitish Metodikasi” Darslarida Kreativ Fikrlashga O‘Rgatishning Samarali Usullari

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo‘lajak boshlang‘ich sinf o‘qituvchilarini interdisiplinar yondashuv asosida tayyorlash jarayoni o‘rganiladi. Xususan, o‘qish savodxonligi va tabiiy fanlarni birlashtirgan holda o‘quvchilarni ta‘limga jalb etishning metodikasi va pedagogik mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi. Bo‘lg‘usi o‘qituvchilarning ta‘lim jarayonidagi pedagogik mahoratini takomillashtirish, fanlar o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro aloqadorlikni o‘quv faoliyatiga tadbiq etishning nazariy va amaliy ishlari ko‘rsatib berildi. Integrativ yondashuv orqali talabalarning fikrlash texnikasini va amaliy bilimlarini tajribalar asosida egallashi samarali tarzda rivojlantirishi aks etgan. Maqolada ushbu yondashuv orqali o‘quvchilarning ko‘p qirrali fikrlashi va amaliy bilimlarni egallashi samarali tarzda shakllantirilishi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: interdisiplinar yondashuv, kreativ fikrlash, o‘qish savodxonligi, pedagogik mahorat, metodika, fanlararo integratsiya, boshlang‘ich ta‘lim.

Kirish (Introduction) One of the urgent tasks facing the education system of the 21st century is the comprehensive formation of skills and knowledge in students. Therefore, ensuring interdisciplinary integration in modern education is considered an important direction. Interdisciplinary education means teaching different disciplines by combining them into a single system of lessons. This approach forms deeper, logical and broader thinking skills in students, and provides the opportunity to analyze problems from different angles. In international experience, many countries have achieved success by introducing an interdisciplinary approach to education. In the US and Canadian education systems, the integration of mathematics, natural sciences, engineering and technology into a single educational process within the framework of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Math) programs has become popular [1; 75-b]. This increases the ability of students to combine creative thinking, practical skills and technical knowledge. In the Finnish education system, an interdisciplinary approach has been widely used for many years, combining all disciplines and providing practical knowledge in the process of solving various problems. In the country, various topics, such as climate change or the development of technologies, are taught through several subjects, which increases children's interest in science and demonstrates the application of knowledge to real life. In Uzbekistan, in recent years, great attention has been paid to interdisciplinary education. In 2020, it is planned to organize classes in Uzbekistan that combine natural sciences and technologies within the framework of the “STEAM Education”

project. Also, through the National Program for Improving the Quality of Education, the country's schools have begun to modernize the education system by integrating subjects. Experiences in teaching mathematics, physics, and technology in an interconnected manner are being introduced in presidential schools and newly established specialized educational institutions.

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlarning tahlili (Literature review). To analyze its place in the training of primary school teachers, several important literatures were analyzed below and important recommendations were made: Fogarty discusses how curricula can be integrated, methods for strengthening the connection between disciplines, and the role of teachers in this process; [2; p. 14] Bybee's work provides extensive information on STEAM education (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Math). Through the STEAM approach, he describes methods for combining natural sciences and technology and delivering practical skills to students; [2; p. 33.] Beane discusses the development of a democratic education model through interdisciplinary integration, and how to prepare students to solve real-life problems by integrating curricula; [3; p. 71.] Paris and Stahl discuss the role of educators in developing students' reading literacy in primary education, practical exercises, and methods of working on texts [4; p. 5], and scientist and methodologist Harlen discusses how to convey natural sciences to students in a simple and interesting way, and how to organize laboratory exercises effectively; [5; p. 21] Meier, D. R., & Wood, L. The Young Child's Memory for Words: Developing First and Second Language and Literacy. This book studies methods for developing children's language learning skills and reading literacy [6; p. 46].

Researcher T. Ziyodova discusses the formation of students' text creation skills in native language classes; N. Bekniyazova studied the methodology of teaching text creation in primary education native language lessons, Sh. Sariyev studied the methodological problems of developing speech through working on the text in primary school reading lessons.

In recent years, many research works have been carried out to achieve high efficiency in reading literacy lessons in primary school. In particular, the problems of forming cognitive processes of primary school students, working on a literary text, improving the system of tasks in accordance with international assessment programs, and studying literary and theoretical concepts were studied in the research of researchers such as H. Bakiyeva, Sh. Sariyev, G. Mamatova, Sh. Boltayeva, L. Muminova. [7; p. 29]

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi (Research Methodology). This scientific article used the author's method called "Everest" on the topic.

Analysis and results. Paying attention to these aspects when creating new generation textbooks will help students studying in the pedagogical field to ensure their students' successful participation in international PIRLS or TIMSS programs in their future educational activities, and most importantly, to develop life skills. Working on the text of a work is an emotional process, and as the content of literary education expands and becomes more complex, students' learning activity should be strengthened in order to achieve mastery. Because being able to interest students in working on the text of a work is to form the skills of understanding, comprehension and perception of the content of the subject, the literary work being read. [8; p. 68]

The teaching specialist must know and distinguish the meanings of the terms didactic process, method, method, tool, pedagogical factor, methodological factor, and planning of educational material. The effectiveness of education largely depends on the correct organization of the didactic process by the teacher. The following methods are effective in developing creativity:

Group projects - create opportunities for students to work together creatively.

Interactive classes - enrich the learning process with the help of modern information technologies.

Distance learning - is used as an alternative tool for developing creativity.

Studies have shown that role-playing, that is, role-playing games, is an effective way to develop creative thinking. In addition, techniques such as "Building logical chains" stimulate students' logical and creative thinking.

Tahlil va natijalar (Analysis and results). Children's vocabulary is expanded through literary texts, poems and folk proverbs. For example, by putting proverbs from Uzbek literature into context, students discover the meaning of different words. Games such as "Build a sentence from a word", "Colorful sentences" or "Multiple meanings of a word" develop creative thinking. Solving text problems, for example, students are given the task of starting a fictional story and creatively continuing its ending.

Also, through the use of literary materials, children can develop imagination, creativity and a critical approach:

Xulosa va takliflar (Conclusion/Recommendations). The use of an international research approach in the creative processing of linguistic and literary materials develops higher-level thinking in children. The connection between different disciplines through an interdisciplinary approach forms a more comprehensive set of creative skills in students. In order to develop creativity in primary grades, it is necessary to widely use problem tasks, creative games, and text-based work methods.

There are many interesting methods and experiments used to develop the ability to understand the text in primary grades. These methods help to increase students' interest in reading, ensure a deeper understanding of the content of the text, and encourage them to think creatively. Below are several interesting approaches and scientific recommendations:

Working with fantasy and creative thinking. To develop students' creative abilities, it is necessary to widely use fantasy and imagination. For example: Continuing writing: Read the introduction to a story to students and ask them to think about how to continue it. This develops their ability to imagine events in advance and create the ending of the story according to their imagination.

Communicating with characters: Communication and interaction can be enhanced by giving students the opportunity to write letters to the characters in the text, share events or feelings from their lives with them.

Using the "Three Traffic Lights" method based on the "Interesting Facts" technique. In this case, the teacher reads the given text with the students and gets acquainted with it. After that, the teacher randomly distributes red, yellow and green cards with traffic light colors to the students. The student in red brings a dictionary of words that require explanation in the text and explains it. The student in yellow must focus on the times and dates in the text and explain them. The student in green must name the people and characters mentioned in the text. Based on the text, select various interesting facts and present them to small groups. For example, by providing additional information about the place or telling stories about historical figures, students can improve their understanding of the context of the text.

Text quiz: Students demonstrate their understanding of the text by taking quizzes or small competitions with questions related to the content of the text. This method increases competition and interest.

Using multimedia Various multimedia tools can be used to enhance text understanding:

Videos and animations: Students can be helped to understand the content of the text more clearly by showing them short videos, animations, or staged stories based on the text. For example, children can bring the events to life in their imagination by seeing the characters in the text talking to each other or by depicting the development of the story.

Audio books: Give students the opportunity to receive the text through listening. This method develops students' auditory perception skills and provides a stronger mastery of various aspects of their reading skills.

Cross-cultural Reading Method Students can be exposed to many cultural ideas by presenting them with different cultural contexts:

Folktales and cultural stories: By selecting fairy tales or stories from different nations and comparing them with each other, students can be introduced to different cultures and values. This method is effective in developing new skills for them.

Cultural exchange: Conducting conversations and presentations about different cultural heroes, while enriching students' spiritual and educational knowledge, broadens their worldview.

Scientific recommendations based on pedagogical and psychological research are also important in this process:

Carol Ann Tomlinson says about differentiated instruction: "Each student has unique abilities and capabilities. Therefore, giving text analysis tasks at different levels of difficulty will make students more interested and allow them to succeed."

Richard E. Mayer emphasizes the positive impact of multimedia tools on students' perception and comprehension in cognitive learning. He recommends using multimedia to better explain text content and using visual materials.

These methods and approaches can help elementary school students develop their text comprehension skills and make the process more interesting, interactive, and creative.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati (References).

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